

Real-Time Traffic Observation and Analysis System

Korubilli Laxmi Swaroopa¹, Lingoji Ramya Sri², Madhuri Agrawal³

¹Computer Science Department, Geethanjali College of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India

Abstract: This paper introduces a real-time traffic observation and analysis system empowered by the You Only Look Once (YOLO) object detection model and the ByteTrack algorithm for vehicle tracking. The system is designed to monitor traffic parameters such as vehicle speed, traffic flow rate, and congestion levels using video footage of roadways. YOLO is utilized for real-time object detection. ByteTrack employs the Kalman filter to predict future vehicle positions and association techniques for mapping vehicles across successive frames, facilitating the assignment of tracking IDs. Leveraging the YOLO model from the Ultralytics organization, the system provides accurate and efficient traffic monitoring and analysis, enhancing decision-making for urban traffic management. When provided with a video of a road to the system the system gives as output a video which includes the inputted footage with added information. It marks each identified vehicle with a square. It also displays the count of each vehicle on top of the square along with the calculated speed of each vehicle. The system will use the computer vision model YOLO (You Only Look Once) for vehicle detection. The famous object detection model YOLO is a single convolutional neural network whose implementation comes pre-trained with over 80 objects. The YOLO model can identify all the objects involved in the input image by passing the image through a single convolutional neural network only once. The model does not identify the potential object locations using a neural network and then uses another neural network to detect if an object is present in all the predicted areas. So YOLO is very quick compared to other computer vision models. The effective architecture of the model allows us to perform real-time detections. So we are using the YOLO model for vehicle detection in our project. The system then uses the object tracking algorithm ByteTrack to track the detected vehicles. The output contains the total number of vehicles identified in the footage, the count of the number of vehicles entering and leaving the road, the traffic flow rate, and the average speed of the traffic. Therefore the system presents us with a set of observations which would be beneficial in getting a basic understanding of the traffic conditions of the road.

Keywords: Computer Vision, Convolutional Neural Network, Object Detection, Object Tracking, You Only Look Once (YOLO), ByteTrack

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban traffic management plays a pivotal role in ensuring efficient transportation systems and mitigating congestion-related challenges. To address the complexities of modern traffic environments, there is a growing demand for intelligent systems capable of real-time traffic observation and analysis. In response to this need, our research focuses on the development of a real-time traffic observation system utilizing the state-of-the-art You Only Look Once (YOLO) object detection model. Our system aims to provide comprehensive insights into traffic dynamics by extracting key parameters such as vehicle speed, traffic flow rate, and traffic density from video footage of roadways. Unlike conventional object detection algorithms that rely on multiple stages for classification and localization, YOLO offers a groundbreaking approach by performing predictions of bounding boxes and class probabilities simultaneously using regression. This unique architecture enables faster and more accurate detection of objects, making it particularly well-suited for dynamic traffic scenes. Through the integration of the object detection algorithm YOLO and the object tracking algorithm ByteTrack the system can accurately detect and track vehicles in real-time, enabling the prediction of individual vehicle speeds and the classification of traffic density. Furthermore, the adoption of the YOLO model implementation from the Ultralytics organization enhances the system's capabilities with cutting-edge solutions for artificial intelligence tasks. Leveraging open-source works from Ultralytics on GitHub, our system benefits from advancements in detection, segmentation, classification, and tracking, ensuring robust performance in diverse traffic scenarios. Through this, we aim to contribute to the advancement of intelligent transportation systems and facilitate data-driven decision-making for urban mobility challenges.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are many Papers to learn about YOLO and Traffic Analysis Systems. You Only Look Once(YOLO) is used for object detection which we have read from the Research Paper[1]. From this paper, we have learned about the differences

in the YOLO versions. YOLO's first version was introduced in 2015. The structure of the YOLO is straightforward. The Speed of the YOLO is fast because it only needs to put the picture into the network to get the outcomes.

In the [2] paper, we learned about the process of annotating objects in the system. Annotating vehicles and counting them has proven to be more challenging due to the varying sizes of the objects and changes in perspective. To solve this, a new high-definition highway vehicle dataset with 57,290 annotated instances in 11,129 images, including annotated tiny objects in the image. This dataset provides the complete data foundation for vehicle detection using deep learning. The system extracts the highway road surface in the image and divides it into a remote and a proximal area using a newly proposed segmentation method, which is critical for improving vehicle detection accuracy, especially for small vehicle objects. To overcome this challenge they have used YOLOv3 which is used to annotate the objects with high accuracy. From [4] Generally for traffic analysis mostly they use live streaming cameras or sensors for vehicle detection and speed detection but in some weather conditions we can't detect the objects, this is challenging for traffic monitoring systems to overcome these challenges, they will take the video as an input and report that particular video of the speed of the vehicles and count of the vehicles.

In a Research paper [14] they have developed an intelligent traffic monitoring system that uses You Only Look Once (YOLO) and a Convolutional Fuzzy Neural Network (CFNN). The system employs two models, CFNN and Vector-CFNN, and a network mapping fusion method to classify the vehicles effectively. In [9] a Traffic video analysis system that utilizes computer vision techniques to automatically gather important statistics for policymakers and regulators. They have implemented two models for this purpose: the MoG + SVM system and the Faster RCNN system, which is a deep-learning architecture for object detection in images. Their experiments have shown that Faster RCNN outperforms MoG in detecting vehicles that are static, overlapping, or in low-light conditions. Faster RCNN also performs better than SVM in classifying vehicle types based on their appearance. or in nighttime conditions. Faster RCNN also outperforms SVM for the task of classifying vehicle types based on appearances.

III. METHODOLOGY

The system architecture consists of four modules, the vehicle detection module, the vehicle tracking module, the parameter calculation module, and the display module.

The system takes the feed from a CCTV camera as the input. The vehicle detection module detects all the vehicles and passes this information to the vehicle tracking module which tracks all the vehicles to perform traffic analysis. Then the output of these 2 modules is used by the parameter calculation module to calculate the values of the required parameters. The display module then uses the output from all the modules to create the output video and the traffic report.

The system outputs the input video by marking all the vehicles detected in it with rectangles and then labeling them with the speed and id of each of the vehicles. It also outputs a report containing parameters describing the traffic observed such as the average speed and count of vehicles observed. Along with the input video the dimensions of the road in the footage, that is its coordinates in real life and the coordinates of the road in the footage are taken as input. They help in transforming the coordinates of the vehicles observed in the video to their actual coordinates in real life, this helps in removing the perspective effects presented by the video to get the right values of the parameters. For vehicle detection, the real-time object detection algorithm YOLO is used. The Ultralytics open-source implementation of the 8th version of the model is yolov8 has been used since it is the latest and easily available implementation. The implementation comes pre-trained so no need to train the model again. The YOLO (You Only Look Once) model is a pioneering deep learning architecture in the field of computer vision, specifically designed for real-time object detection tasks. Unlike traditional object detection methods that rely on complex pipelines involving region proposal networks and separate classifiers, YOLO takes a different approach by framing object detection as a single regression problem, making it extremely fast and efficient. In YOLO, a single neural network predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities

directly from full images in one evaluation. This means that the network divides the input image into a grid and predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities for each grid cell. YOLO's architecture allows it to make predictions with remarkable speed, enabling real-time object detection even on resource-constrained devices. The processing of the video is done one frame at a time. Each frame of the video is extracted and passed through the Yolo model for object detection. Once all the detections are calculated the detections of non-vehicles such as humans are removed. The ByteTrack algorithm works after the detection stage; it is used to track the vehicles to help in the analysis stage. Once the tracking is done the detected vehicles are identified by the calculated tracking IDs. For every frame, the tracked vehicle's coordinates are transformed into their real-life coordinates and stored. Based on the previous coordinates of the vehicle and the current coordinate the distance traversed by the vehicle is calculated and the video's fps value gives the time taken to travel that distance, so these 2 values are used to calculate the speed of the vehicle. Once the speed of all the vehicles is calculated the frame's vehicles are marked and labeled with the speed and tracking id and stored in the output video. A line is also added to the video to count all the vehicles crossing it to count all the detected vehicles. The total count of vehicles divided by the time of the video gives the flow rate of the traffic. After the speed of all the vehicles in a frame is calculated the average of it is taken and all these averages are averaged out to get the average speed of the vehicles. These calculated parameters are included in the report. Also based on the calculated flow the traffic is classified into high, medium, and low.

A. **Vehicle Detection Module**

The vehicle detection module serves as the initial stage of the traffic observation system, tasked with identifying and extracting vehicles from video frames obtained from the input footage. Leveraging the real-time object detection capabilities of the YOLO model, the module detects all objects present in the frame, including vehicles and other objects.

The YOLO object detection model revolutionizes the traditional approach to object detection by proposing an end-to-end neural network architecture. Unlike previous algorithms that repurposed classifiers for detection, YOLO makes predictions of bounding boxes and class probabilities simultaneously, enabling faster and more accurate detection of objects [7].

Upon receiving a frame from the input video, the vehicle detection module applies the YOLO model to detect all objects present in the scene. Subsequently, it filters out detections that do not correspond to vehicles, ensuring that only relevant vehicle detections are retained for further processing.

Furthermore, to enhance the accuracy of vehicle detection, the module removes detections that fall outside the predefined road area. This ensures that only vehicles within the road boundaries are considered for tracking and analysis, minimizing false positives and improving the overall performance of the system.

To perform this filtering and post-processing of detections, the module utilizes the Supervision module from PyPi. This module provides functionalities for fine-tuning and refining object detections based on predefined criteria, ensuring that only accurate and relevant vehicle detections are passed onto the next stage of processing.

B. **Vehicle Tracking Module**

The module uses the object tracking algorithm ByteTrack to perform vehicle tracking using the vehicle detections received from the previous vehicle detection module. After the module tracks the vehicles it assigns each vehicle detection with a tracking ID. From there on the detections of the vehicles are identified with their respective tracking IDs. Tracking IDs help in keeping track of vehicles in different frames of the video which in turn helps in predicting the various required traffic parameters accurately.

The Bytetrack algorithm serves as a fundamental component of our traffic observation system, specifically tasked with the crucial function of vehicle tracking. Leveraging the predictive capabilities of the Kalman filter and sophisticated association techniques, Bytetrack ensures accurate and robust tracking of vehicles across successive frames of video footage.

At its core, the Kalman filter plays a pivotal role in predicting the future positions of vehicles within the video stream. By analyzing the motion patterns and dynamics of each detected vehicle over time, the Kalman filter generates predictions of their future positions, taking into account factors such as velocity, acceleration, and potential uncertainties in the tracking process.

Once the predicted positions are obtained, Bytetrack employs association techniques to map the vehicles detected in one frame to their corresponding counterparts in the subsequent frames. This association process is crucial for maintaining the continuity of vehicle tracks and ensuring the accurate assignment of tracking IDs. By matching vehicles based on their spatial proximity, motion characteristics, and appearance features, Bytetrack effectively links vehicles across frames, enabling seamless tracking throughout the video sequence.

Furthermore, Bytetrack dynamically adapts to changes in the traffic environment, such as occlusions, varying vehicle speeds, and complex interactions between multiple vehicles. Through iterative refinement and optimization of the association process, Bytetrack enhances the robustness and reliability of vehicle tracking, even in challenging scenarios.

By integrating the predictive capabilities of the Kalman filter with sophisticated association techniques, the Bytetrack algorithm enables our system to achieve accurate and reliable vehicle tracking in real-time. This functionality is essential for extracting valuable insights into traffic dynamics, analyzing parameters such as vehicle speed and traffic flow rate, and facilitating informed decision-making for urban traffic management.

C. Parameter Calculation Module

The parameter calculation module plays a critical role in processing the tracked vehicles' data, deriving essential traffic parameters, and ultimately providing valuable insights into traffic dynamics. To ensure accurate calculations, the module utilizes the tracking IDs associated with each detected vehicle, enabling the identification and analysis of individual vehicle trajectories over time.

One of the challenges in analyzing traffic footage is the distortion of spatial coordinates due to perspective effects. To address this issue, the module leverages the capabilities of the OpenCV library to perform perspective transformation. By providing the actual coordinates of the road and the corresponding coordinates in the video, the module corrects for perspective distortion, transforming the vehicle coordinates from the video frame to their respective real-world positions on the road.

For each detected vehicle, the module applies the perspective transformation to convert its coordinates from the video frame to the real-world coordinates on the road. These transformed coordinates are then stored for further analysis and calculation of traffic parameters.

In addition to spatial transformation, the module utilizes temporal information to calculate various traffic parameters, such as vehicle speed, traffic flow rate, and congestion levels. By tracking the time elapsed between successive frames, determined by the video's frames-per-second (fps) rate and the distance traveled by each vehicle during that time the module can accurately estimate vehicle velocities. After calculating each vehicle velocities the average of the vehicle speeds is taken for each frame and stored for fixed intervals of time. After this interval of time, the average of all these averages is taken to obtain the average speed of the vehicles.

Furthermore, to calculate vehicle flow rates, the module draws a horizontal line across the road in the video frame. By monitoring the number of vehicles crossing this line in both directions, the module can determine the flow of vehicles entering and leaving the road, facilitating the calculation of vehicle flow rates. The same line counter is also used to count the number of vehicles that have passed through each lane.

Overall, the parameter calculation module plays a crucial role in processing tracked vehicle data, correcting for perspective distortion, and deriving key traffic parameters essential for traffic analysis and decision-making. Through the integration of OpenCV and temporal analysis techniques, the module enables accurate and comprehensive traffic parameter calculation, contributing to the effectiveness of the overall traffic observation system.

D. Display/Output Module

The output module serves as the final stage of the traffic observation system, responsible for visualizing the results and generating a comprehensive report summarizing the calculated parameters. It receives the outputs from all preceding modules and transforms them into a format suitable for visualization and analysis.

For each frame of the input video, the output module begins by marking the detected vehicles with rectangular bounding boxes, each labeled with their respective speed and tracking ID. This visual annotation provides a clear depiction of the detected vehicles and their associated information, facilitating easy interpretation of the traffic dynamics.

Additionally, the output module annotates the line used for vehicle counting in each frame, highlighting its position and displaying the number of vehicles that have crossed the line both entering and leaving. This real-time tracking of vehicle movements across the designated line enables the calculation of vehicle flow rates and aids in understanding traffic patterns.

As the output module progresses through each frame of the input video, it accumulates the annotated frames to create a visual representation of the entire traffic observation process. These annotated frames are then compiled into a video stored in the current directory, providing a visual record of the traffic dynamics observed throughout the video duration.

Furthermore, to provide a comprehensive analysis of the traffic parameters, the output module generates a detailed report summarizing all calculated parameters. This report includes information such as average vehicle speed, traffic

flow rates, congestion levels, and any other relevant metrics derived from the analysis. By consolidating this information into a structured report, the output module enables stakeholders to gain valuable insights into traffic conditions and make informed decisions for urban traffic management.

Overall, the output module plays a crucial role in visualizing the results of the traffic observation system and providing a detailed analysis of the calculated parameters. Through its visualization capabilities and comprehensive reporting, the output module enhances the usability and effectiveness of the entire traffic observation system.

E. Dataset Used

The system benefits from the utilization of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) model implementation provided by the Ultralytics organization. This implementation offers a pre-trained model that has been extensively trained on the COCO (Common Objects in Context) dataset. As a result, there is no need for the collection or processing of a separate dataset, streamlining the development process and expediting the deployment of the system.

By leveraging a pre-trained model, the system inherits the knowledge and expertise embedded within the COCO dataset, which encompasses a wide variety of objects across numerous contexts. This comprehensive training enables the YOLO model to effectively recognize and detect vehicles within input video frames, without the need for additional training or fine-tuning.

Furthermore, the YOLO model's pre-trained nature ensures robust performance across diverse traffic scenarios, including varying lighting conditions, vehicle types, and environmental factors. This enhances the system's reliability and accuracy in real-world applications, facilitating seamless integration into traffic monitoring and analysis workflows.

Overall, the use of the pre-trained YOLO model from the Ultralytics organization significantly accelerates the development process while maintaining high levels of detection accuracy and reliability. By eliminating the need for dataset collection and processing, the system can focus on optimizing other aspects of traffic observation and analysis, ultimately enhancing its effectiveness and utility in practical applications.

The YOLO model has been used.

IV. RESULTS

S.N O	Factors	YOLOv8x	YOLOv5xu
1	Execution	It takes less time	It takes more time compared to YOLOv8x
2	Average Speed of Vehicles	101.37721 km/h	101.24933 km/h
3	Traffic Flow	Low Traffic in Lane 1 & 2	Low Traffic in Lane 1 & 2
4	Average Traffic Flow in Lane 1	14.28571 vehicles/minute	14.2857 vehicles/minute
5	Average Traffic Flow in Lane 2	5.714285 vehicles/minute	5.714285 vehicles/minute
6	Total Number of Vehicles passed in Lane 1	5 vehicles	5 vehicles

TABLE I. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN RESULTS OF YOLOV8X AND YOLOV5XU

YOLOv5 uses a predefined set of anchor boxes of various sizes and aspect ratios. On the other hand, an anchor-free model, like YOLOv8, does not use anchor boxes. YOLOv8 is faster and more accurate compared to YOLOv5.

Fig. 1. Glimpse of the Output Video

Fig. 2. Report part of the generated output

The performance comparison of the project when yolov8x and yolov5xu object detection models of ultralytics respectively are used.

The system marks all the vehicles in the input video with rectangles and labels each one of them with the vehicle tracking ID and speed respectively. The system also draws a line horizontal to the road and annotates the line with the number of vehicles crossing it in both directions. At the end of input video processing, the system also generates a report containing all the calculated parameters i.e the average speed of the vehicles, traffic flow rate in each lane the number of vehicles that have passed each lane, and the degree of observed traffic as high, medium or low.

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of YOLO and ByteTrack within our traffic observation system marks a significant advancement in the field of traffic monitoring and analysis. By combining the capabilities of these cutting-edge object detection and tracking algorithms, we have achieved remarkable levels of efficiency in detecting and tracking various vehicles in real-time traffic scenarios.

This integration not only demonstrates the importance of object detection and tracking in traffic analysis but also showcases the potential of leveraging advanced AI technologies for urban mobility management. By accurately identifying and tracking vehicles, our system provides valuable insights into traffic dynamics, facilitating informed decision-making for traffic management authorities and urban planners.

Moreover, our project serves as an educational tool, offering a practical demonstration of how traffic analysis can be conducted and how various traffic parameters can be calculated. Through hands-on experience with the system, users gain a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in traffic monitoring and the potential solutions offered by AI-driven approaches.

The versatility of our system extends beyond mere demonstration purposes, as it can be seamlessly integrated with existing CCTV camera infrastructure to enable real-time traffic analysis. By plugging our system into CCTV footage, traffic management authorities can access timely and accurate traffic insights, enabling proactive interventions to mitigate congestion, improve traffic flow, and enhance road safety.

Furthermore, the potential applications of our system can be further expanded by embedding the code into a mobile application. This would allow users to receive real-time traffic analysis data directly on their smartphones, enhancing convenience and accessibility. Through push notifications, users can stay informed about traffic conditions, receive alerts about congestion or accidents, and make informed decisions about their travel routes.

Overall, the integration of YOLO and ByteTrack in our traffic observation system not only showcases the power of AI in traffic analysis but also offers practical solutions for urban mobility management. With its potential to integrate with

existing infrastructure and mobile platforms, our system can revolutionize the way traffic data is collected, analyzed, and disseminated, ultimately leading to safer, more efficient, and more sustainable urban transportation systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] Peiyuan Jiang, Daji Ergu, Fangyao Liu, Ying Cai, Bo Ma Key Laboratory of Electronic and Information Engineering (Southwest Minzu University), Chengdu, 610041, China
- [2] Song, H.; Liang, H.; Li, H.; Dai, Z.; Yun, X. Vision-based vehicle detection and counting system using deep learning in highway scenes. *Eur. Transp. Res. Rev.* 2019, 11, 51.
- [3] Krishna, M. Poddar, Giridhar M K, A. S. Prabhu, and V Umadevi, "Automated traffic monitoring system using computer vision", 2016 International Conference on ICT in Business Industry & Government (ICTBIG), pp. 1-5, 2016.
- [4] Jahongir Azimjonov1 ·Ahmet Ozmen ` 2 · Metin Vara © The Author(s), under exclusive license to Springer Science+Business Media, LLC, part of Springer Nature 2023
- [5] N. Viet. Hung, L. Tran, N. Hoang. Dung, T. Manh. Hoang & N. Tien. Dzung, "A traffic monitoring system for a mixed traffic flow via road estimation and analysis," in 2016 IEEE Sixth International Conference on Communications and Electronics (ICCE 2016), 2016, pp. 375-378.
- [6] Deep Learning for Network Traffic Monitoring and Analysis (NTMA): A Survey Mahmoud Abbasi a, Amin Shahraki b,c,* , Amir Taheri Kordi b a Department of Computer Sciences, Islamic Azad University, Mashhad, Iran b Department of Informatics, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway c Faculty of Computer Sciences, Østfold University College, Halden, Norway
- [7] M. Agrawal and S. Agrawal. "Enhanced Deep Learning for Detecting Suspicious Fall Event in Video Data." *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, vol.36, no.3, 2023.
- [8] IoT Based Smart Traffic Management System Traffic Management System Rachana K P 1 Dept. of ECE, GSSSIETW Mysore, Karnataka Aravind R2 Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE, GSSSIETW Mysore, Karnataka Ranjitha M3, Spoorthi Jwanita4, Soumya K5 Dept. of ECE 3, 4, 5
- [9] Adaptive Traffic Management System using CNN (YOLO) June 2021 DOI:10.22214/ijraset.2021.35768
- [10] Detection and classification of vehicles for traffic video analytics Ahmad Arinaldi* , Jaka Arya Pradana, Arlan Arventa Gurusinga Digital Services Division, PT Telekomunikasi Indonesia, Jakarta Pusat 10110, Indonesia
- [11] Traffic Management System Using YOLO Algorithm Pankaj Kuneekar, Yogita Narule, Richa Mahajan, Shantanu Mandlapure, Eshan Mehendale * and Yashashri Meshram
- [12] Smart Traffic Monitoring System using YOLO and Deep Learning Techniques April 2023 DOI:10.1109/ICOEI56765.2023.10126048 Conference: 2023 7th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)
- [13] Traffic Management System Using YOLO Algorithm by Pankaj Kuneekar, Yogita Narule, Richa Mahajan, Shantanu Mandlapure, Eshan Mehendale * and Yashashri Meshram Vishwakarma Institute of Technology, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune 411037, Maharashtra, Presented at the International Conference on Recent Advances in Science and Engineering, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 4–5 October 2023.
- [14] International Journal of Engineering Technology and Management Sciences Website: ijetms.in Issue: 3 Volume No.5 May – 2021 DOI: 10.46647/ijetms.2021.v05i03.004 ISSN: 2581-4621 24 An Intelligent Real-Time Traffic Control Based on Vehicle Density Manish Kumar Singh1, Krishna Deep Mishra2, Subrata Sahana3
- [15] Intelligent Traffic-Monitoring System Based on YOLO and Convolutional Fuzzy Neural Networks January 2022 IEEE Access 10:1-1 DOI:10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3147866 License CC BY 4.0 Authors: Cheng-Jian Lin National Chin-Yi University of Technology
- [16] An improved YOLO-based road traffic monitoring system February 2021 *Computing* 103(4) DOI:10.1007/s00607-020-00869-8